

Next Generation Internet boosted by EU-US ecosystem of researchers and innovators

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INTRODUCTION & OVERVIEW

The EU and the US are natural partners in science, technology, and innovation, sharing high interest in cooperation for joint developments. The US as a non-EU and non-associated country remains the leader of participation in EU research and innovation (R&I) programmes¹. This massive scale of US R&I collaborative activities with the EU Member States is grounded under the long-standing EU-US Science and Technology Agreements².

Building upon the EU-US collaboration in previous work programmes, the NGI Explorers Programme was shaped aiming to:

- Enhance EU-US cooperation in Next Generation Internet (NGI);
- Develop interoperable solutions and joint demonstrators, contributing to standards;
- Build an EU-US ecosystem of top researchers, hi-tech startups/SMEs and Internet-related communities collaborating on the evolution of the Internet.

The list of the above cross-cutting priorities was executed through a 3 - 6 months fellowship Programme for researchers³ and innovators⁴ providing financial support for travel and subsistence for 49 successful EU-US formed partnerships during the 3 years of the Programme.

The achievements of these Transatlantic expeditions have built a fertile and collaborative ground for exploring new ideas, products, concepts, methodologies, and foremost exchanging know-how between Explorers and their matched US partners.

The essential role of the Programme turned out to be a bridge of understanding to seemingly contradictory ecosystems needs: academic-driven goals on the one hand with a market/business/product oriented on the other. US universities engaged in the Programme have played a major role in providing cutting-edge expertise on specific topics.

Thanks to the Programme participation, researchers came to conclusions that while it is often convenient in academia to observe the theoretical aspects of certain problems, it is highly beneficial to associate this problem with business-driven goals. On the other hand, Innovators understood that there are many complementarities between the research team and entrepreneurs, where each brings his/her own valuable insights, especially sound scientific validation for their offerings.

1 https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/europe-world/international-cooperation/united-states_en

2 Agreement for Scientific and Technological Cooperation: governs EU-US research and innovation cooperation. It was first signed in 1998 and is renewed every 5 years; Implementing Arrangement between the European Commission and the Government of the United States of America for cooperation between researchers funded separately by the European Union's and the United States Framework Programmes on Research and Innovation¹ signed on 17 October 2016 by Commissioner Moedas and Anthony L. Gardner, the US Ambassador to the EU; and Agreement for scientific and technological cooperation between the European Community and the Government of the United States - Intellectual property

3 Holding a Master's degree or higher. Employed in third level education institutes, research infrastructures, non-profit organizations and charitable (scientific) foundations and public research centers

4 Internet technologists representing hi-tech startups, micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), mid-caps working on Internet or and other related technologies.

The EC transparently refers that the key to technological success lies in Europe's innovators and researchers. Providing them with an opportunity to international collaborations in science and technology will bring an analogous positive impact on innovation, help expand international mobility and foster research closing the gap in areas like cutting-edge technologies. Therefore, it is crucial to facilitate such collaborative activities beyond Europe, as there are existing legal and administrative obstacles to researchers and innovators on either side of the ocean. The NGI Explorers Programme is a source

of real experiences regarding the administrative battles Explorers had to pass before starting the actual collaboration. We advocate to boost R&I cooperation by offering both sides a favourable opportunity to work together, minimizing the bureaucratic efforts, improving access conditions and legal hurdles to complex IP regulations. As a result we can leverage effects of R&I partnerships with US counterparts.

ANALYSIS OF THE EXPLORERS' INTERVIEWS

The feedback gathered from the Explorers about the NGI Explorers Programme serves as the fundamental base for this policy brief. In fact, both positive and negative feedback will constitute the starting point for improvements for a future next generation program, going beyond continental boundaries for further transatlantic collaboration.

It has been clearly defined by the participating Explorers that the NGI Explorers Programme is seen as a highly desirable initiative for early startup founders seeking scientific validation for their products or services, where it is extremely hard to secure external funding if not affiliated to the academic world. Many have mentioned that a Programme such as this serves as a crucial platform for meeting new people and creating long-term connections that are enriching both at personal level and at career level for all parties involved. It also allowed academia and the business world to collide, creating synergies that are not possible in traditional programs as they tend to be strictly academic exchanges. Thanks to this, many of the Explorers were able to find complementary aspects to their own backgrounds and knowledge, training in fundamental topics that they did not have the chance to explore before. In this regard, the many workshops and training offered by the NGI Explorers Programme and TETRA, including the bootcamp prior to the

beginning of the expeditions proved to be valued elements for personal growth and fine tuning skills crucial for a steady career development.

The global pandemic has majorly affected the NGI Explorers journeys, forcing much of the work to be done in remote form as COVID restrictions made it impossible to travel or put a large amount of restrictions on VISA applications.

While a few Explorers admitted that working in remote form was no issue, many expressed the opinion that remote work took away much of the core experience from the Programme. In fact, the majority agree that it is crucial in a Programme such as this, to work in person, sharing an environment with your collaborator so as to expand soft skills, and network.

Regardless of additional restrictions due to COVID, most Explorers, if not all, expressed that a major concern and point of improvement is the very long bureaucratic process accompanying the visa application that allows European researchers or innovators to travel and stay in the United States of America for a certain amount of time to carry out a project. The process as it is right now requires too many steps and people involved. There should be a major reduction of bureaucratic technicalities. Some Explorers provided suggestions on this matter:

- VISA priority and application express lanes for all researchers and innovators that apply for a research stay backed up by a program such as the NGI Explorers Programme. This implies less restrictions on programmes that promote transatlantic research and development collaborations.
- Establishing a memorandum of agreement (pre-agreement) between the European Commission and the US institution in charge for such expeditions in order to speed up the VISA application process.

Another important concern is the IP negotiations. One of the Explorers suggests providing the Explorers with two options:

- Offering an agreed upon IP agreement from the US node, where mutual/joint ownership is offered.
- Leaving it open for individuals who can negotiate better terms.

More advice and guidance on the commercialization or property of the final products and services created would be appreciated.

There have been contradicting opinions about the amount of time allocated to each project. A few felt that the time given was too short,

considering that a minimum of 30-45 days is required for proper background and state-of-the-art mastery before collaborating with doctoral students with a few years of experience in their specific fields. In this case a 4-month expedition for pure research projects is recommended (without the implementation in software) and a 6+ month expedition for projects aiming commercialization/licensing or any other form of business activity.

But many of the Explorers felt that the duration of 3 or 6 months was perfect for their needs.

As for deliverables, it was suggested to differentiate between architectural and algorithmic design, and software implementation which in general is more time consuming but provides the entire case for business and financial exploitation. In addition, the programme should keep a time buffer between the Open Call and the actual travel considering all possible contingencies, together with a well-thought plan for time allocation when it comes to accommodation search and VISA application processes.

The implementation of these suggestions coming directly from participating innovators and researchers will lead to a concrete qualitative leap for future programs.

US NODES PERSPECTIVES

The US nodes, therefore the host institutions for our European innovators and researchers across the United States, represent a core part of this collective journey of ongoing efforts to strengthen the EU-US cooperative and vibrant ecosystem. Their feedback is as important as the one received from the NGI Explorers.

According to the information gathered, these institutions recognize great added value in the offer of programmes such as ours. In fact, they see great potential in building strong collaborations between US and EU bright minds. What they require is the creation of more programmes that facilitate this exchange for both academics and non academic individuals with great ideas in the realm of emerging technologies.

Just as the Explorers, they also support the notion that the bureaucratic process should be thinned out, making it easier for institutions to create opportunities for European innovators and researchers, thus investing in potent synergies that could be extremely beneficial for all involved.

CONCLUSIONS

The NGI Explorers Programme is the beginning of mutually beneficial, long term transatlantic collaboration supporting progress in the field of emerging technologies. This Programme will pave the way for additional collaboration in the future, with long term benefits. In fact, programmes such as this make it possible for innovators and researchers alike, even without academic affiliations to expand their horizons both personally and professionally. It allows for individuals to undertake a journey that can overlook budgetary and logistic obstacles, backed up by a solid programme.

After careful consideration of the entirety of the feedback collected from participating NGI Explorers, we can conclude that programmes such as the NGI Explorers are vital for researchers and innovators looking to expand their network, knowledge, skills and projects in an environment of international weight. This transatlantic collaboration is fundamental for European

progress, in a future where emerging technologies will be crucial for advancements across industries. For this reason it is important to facilitate such programs in the future, reducing bureaucratic processes and creating fast lane VISA processes for researchers and innovators wishing to conduct their projects in another continent. The same can be said for institutions such as the Universities involved in the NGI Explorers programme in the US, which rely on programmes such as this to create the opportunity for knowledge exchange with European researchers and innovators. The synergies exist, all that remains is to find the best way to facilitate the exploration of this for global progress.

